

INTERPRETATION OF OUR NATIONAL VALUES IN THE “POSITION OF TEMUR”.

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Annotation:

In the article we see that the teachings and works of Sahibkiran Amir Temur were created on the basis of the idea that the spiritual maturity of a person can only be achieved on the basis of possessing high morality and mastering science. The views of our great-grandfather Amir Temur on domestic cultural life are set out in his invaluable work “Tuzuklari Temur”.

Keywords: national, entrepreneur, spirituality, state, great, personality, heritage, country, art.

The culture of the peoples of Central Asia is proud of its great thinkers who brought the culture of the peoples of the Middle Ages to the forefront of world culture. We always carefully study the spiritual and cultural heritage created as a result of the teachings, knowledge and experiences of our ancestors, and take a step into the future based on the noble ideas contained in them. After all, the thoughts expressed by our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev show how important they are today. Our Head of State: We have a great history worthy of admiration. We have great ancestors worthy of admiration. We have incomparable wealth worthy of admiration. And I believe that if we are lucky, we will certainly have a great future worthy of admiration, great literature and art. [1; 482 p.]

Indeed, the rare works of our encyclopedic scientists play a huge role in the development of science and cultural life not only in our country, but also in the whole world. The peoples of the East have long produced many creators who have contributed to the treasury of world culture with their classic works. Bringing their heritage to the general public is extremely necessary for the prosperity of our culture. Today, there are many problems in the field of preserving and developing Uzbek national culture and spirituality, and it is important to preserve and determine its place in the upbringing of the younger generation. In this era of increasing technology and information flows, it is of course important to show the growing younger generation its place in determining the direction of progress towards perfection, relying on the cultural and spiritual heritage of their ancestors. The strong social policy being carried out in our country today has demonstrated significant aspects of this issue. During the years of independence, great work has been carried out and is being consistently continued to restore the ancient history and rich culture of our people, to comprehensively study and promote the scientific, religious and spiritual heritage of our great scholars and saints, to improve their holy places, and to educate the younger generation in the spirit of their noble traditions. In particular, if we consider the teachings and works of Sahibkiran Amir Temur, they are based on the assumption that a person’s spiritual perfection can only be achieved through high morality and mastery of science. Our great ancestors Amir Temur’s views on national

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cultural life were expressed in his invaluable work "Temur's Regulations". This work consists of 2 parts. The first part describes the biography, socio-political activities of Amir Temur, his acquisition of central power in Transoxiana, the elimination of political fragmentation, the establishment of a centralized state, his military campaigns, and how he treated various social classes in order to strengthen his vast empire, in a concise manner, using the language of the great Sahibkiran. The second part consists of the famous Jahangir's special testament, advice and teachings to his children. It mainly discusses who to rely on in governing the state, the attitude and duties of the crown and throne holders, the selection of ministers and army leaders, the organization of the army and the rules of warfare, the salary of soldiers, the procedure for governing the country, the duties and responsibilities of statesmen and army leaders, the way to reward emirs, ministers and other officials for their special services to the crown and throne, and others. [1; 482 p.] This work gives a person some kind of spiritual strength, enthusiasm and determination. One can often witness how vital the wise thoughts in the work are, which never get old and are still food for human spirituality today. For example, the words "I have seen in my experience that one person with firm determination, enterprise, alert, courageous and courageous is better than a thousand careless and indifferent people" cannot be denied how important they are spiritually even today.

It should be clear to all of us that where there is carelessness and indifference, where the most urgent issues are carelessly ignored, there spirituality becomes the weakest and weakest point. And on the contrary, where alertness and enthusiasm, high intelligence and thinking prevail, there spirituality becomes a powerful force.

It is also noteworthy that, despite being a strict and demanding head of state and a great commander, Amir Temur always valued scholars and talented people. "Whatever country I conquered, I held in high esteem the dignitaries of that land, I paid homage to and respected its sayyids, scholars, fuzalo and mashayhi, I gave them gifts, tasks and determined their salaries, I saw the great men of that region as my brothers and sisters, and their youth and children as my own children" [3; p. 94]. Indeed, history tells us that as the ruler of a great state, Amir Temur was a patron of religious leaders and spiritually mature intellectuals.

According to the great sahibqira, it is necessary to do good to every person who comes to him, wishing to be kind and compassionate to everyone. "Whoever comes to me from friend to enemy, I have treated my friends in such a way that their enmity has turned into friendship" [3; 63b.]. Wherever a righteous person acts with goodness, kindness and generosity, evil and enmity retreat from there. A person comes to someone with a thousand desires and hopes, seeking salvation through some work, and by easing his difficulty, he not only receives the desired satisfaction, but also does a good deed. This, in turn, creates qualities such as mutual respect, friendship, gratitude and loyalty among people.

It is unchanging that humanity has been fighting idea against idea, idea against idea, and ignorance against enlightenment. The above idea of our wise grandfather is a logical continuation of this philosophy and a summary of his own experience.

In conclusion, it can be said that the study of works such as "Temur's Regulations" plays an important role in instilling in young people not only respect for the heritage of their ancestors, but also the correct formation of their cultural and spiritual consciousness and the development of their human qualities. Through this work, Sahibkiran, with his mature political acumen, care for the representatives of science, art and literature, built a great and powerful empire and achieved a

worthy and strong place in the history of world statehood as a patron of art and culture. After all, the spiritual heritage left by Amir Temur serves as a school of example in forming the ideas of honesty, purity, faith and patriotism in the hearts of the youth of our independent country.

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